

THE IMPORTANCE OF FORMATION OF LIBRARY CULTURE IN MODERN AGE

Egamberdiyev Bahriddin¹

¹ Master of degree Namangan State University

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ABSTRACT

The article presents information on the need to create a sense of spirituality and the role of the culture of reading in youth.

During the years of independence, our country has done a lot to bring up young people spiritually mature and physically healthy, patriotic and selfless, to protect their rights and interests. In order to radically improve the activities in this area and raise them to a new level of quality, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan issued a decree "On increasing the effectiveness of state youth policy and support the activities of the Youth Union of Uzbekistan." The decree clearly states what needs to be done for young people to solve problems and find their place in society.

One of the priorities of our youth is to instill in the minds and hearts of young people a sense of responsibility for the development of the country and the future of the country. In order to fulfill these tasks wisely, it is important to create a sense of involvement among young people. The First President of

Uzbekistan Islam Karimov said that living with a sense of involvement in the events around us is one of the most pressing issues today.

Involvement is an upbringing that builds commitment to future generations. There are many types of involvement in human life. Civic engagement, spiritual engagement, social engagement, and more.

Citizen involvement is a partnership involved in an activity or process. If every citizen lives with a sense of personal involvement in the fate of the Motherland, his duty and responsibility to society will increase. Involvement helps young people to understand the direct connection with the current problems of our time, the need to feel responsible for all that is happening in the world, to feel the mood and interests of those around them, as well as to work with students in this situation. an idea of the means of achieving the goal is formed.

In either case, the teacher confronts the students with a reality related to some kind of spiritual depravity. This situation is emotional (the student imagines how difficult it is for the person), logical (looking for the best ways to solve situations), as well as active (defining his attitude and determining the direction of his behavior in this situation). levels. From the definitions of belonging, we can see that this concept is very important in every aspect of social life.

Spiritual involvement is no exception. Spiritual involvement is a complex concept that expresses the maturity and humanity of a person. One must act systematically in order to cultivate a sense of spiritual belonging. Young people who have developed a sense of spiritual belonging would have contributed to the preservation of the high human qualities of the nation and future generations. The first President Islam Karimov in his book "High spirituality is an invincible force" defined the concept of spirituality as follows: The incomparable power that shoots is the criterion of all his views. Indeed, spirituality is an important part of human life. The process of spirituality and spiritual maturity paves the way for the formation of spiritual involvement.

Reading culture is an important part of this systematic work. The President of the Republic Shavkat Mirziyoyev said that reading a book can solve all possible problems.

The great thinker Alisher Navoi said that every second of reading a book brings you closer to wisdom, which shows the unique role of

reading culture in human life and spiritual maturity.

Whether we refer to the great masterpieces of our national heritage, whether it is modern literature today, or examples of world literature, all of these can be an important factor in the formation of a spiritual worldview and a source of education. There are many observations today about the pros and cons of globalization. While the rise of egocentrism, corruption, and treason is a painful situation, it is even more painful for young people. The root cause of such cases is directly related to the level of spiritual maturity and involvement.

It is important to look for literature that contains ideas that can be used as an example to read, that can serve as a model for thinking, and that can inspire people to grow. There are many factors in a young person's life that can interest them, attract them, and penetrate their minds and worldviews. At the same time, their number is growing. Whether we realize it or not, our young people are affected by such factors. Because some of them do not have a shield to deal with such prejudices, they do not have the moral immunity. Today, there are a variety of books on the shelves that are useful for spiritual development and personal growth. So, today we can't say enough about the quantitative indicators of books. In addition to organizing various competitions to improve the results, reading books in the family, educational institutions, workplaces and meetings with leading representatives of our literature will help to solve the problem.

In order to ensure that young people with a strong interest in the

Internet can enter the world of books from the virtual world, and to achieve the sustainability of this journey, it is necessary to form a conscious attitude towards reading books. The development of electronic versions of fiction books is a

positive solution to this problem. However, we have so many legacies that have not been put into electronic form that it is difficult to achieve spiritual maturity and spiritual involvement without reading them.

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